

GENERAL QUESTIONS

1. Tell me a little about yourself: your educational background, age, and professional trajectory.
 2. Could you tell me a bit about your day-to-day work activities?
 3. Could you tell me how you develop yourself (seek knowledge) in your daily routine?
 4. What motivates you to participate in corporate training programs?
 5. What discourages you from participating in corporate training programs?
-

SPECIFIC QUESTIONS

TRAINING

1. How does the training format (e.g., video classes, live sessions, in-person, etc.) influence your willingness to participate in corporate training?
 2. How does the instructional method of the training (e.g., debates, games, simulations, etc.) influence your willingness to participate in corporate training?
 3. How does the mandatory nature of the training influence your willingness to participate in corporate training?
 4. How does the duration of a class influence your willingness to participate in corporate training?
 5. How does the total workload (training hours) influence your willingness to participate in corporate training?
 6. How does the training content influence your willingness to participate in corporate training?
-

ORGANIZATION

1. How does the organizational climate influence your willingness to participate in corporate training?
 2. How does leadership influence your willingness to participate in corporate training?
 3. How does the relationship between training activities and your work tasks influence your willingness to participate in corporate training?
 4. How does your career planning influence your willingness to participate in corporate training?
 5. How does autonomy in your work influence your willingness to participate in corporate training?
 6. How does your mental workload influence your willingness to participate in corporate training?
-

INDIVIDUAL

1. How do you feel when you know you will participate in a corporate training program whose content seems challenging?
 2. How does the expectation of performing well in a corporate training program influence your willingness to participate?
 3. How do you believe your technical skills influence your willingness to participate in corporate training?
 4. How do you believe you will be able to keep up with the content of the corporate training?
 5. How do you believe your colleagues influence your willingness to participate in corporate training?
-

CLOSING

1. Is there any situation that influenced your participation in corporate training programs that has not yet been mentioned and that you would like to share?
-

QUESTIONS INCLUDED IN INTERVIEWS WITH GROUPS 6 AND 7

1. **Organizational learning culture**

- How do you perceive the company's encouragement for employees to participate in corporate training programs?

2. **Promotion at work**

- How do you perceive the relationship between your performance in training programs and promotion opportunities within the company?

3. **Expectations about the training**

- What do you usually expect from a corporate training program before it begins?

4. **Work engagement**

- How does your work routine interfere with your dedication to the training?

5. **Organizational constraints**

- What factors in the organizational routine influence your participation in corporate training programs?